

Inhibition Of The Impulsive Response Of The Secondary School Students

Jafar J. Jwad

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Abstract

The secondary stage is a sensitive stage in human life, as it complements the stage of adolescence and the various physiological and biological changes that follow that afflict the psychological and social life of the human being, and it represents preparing the adolescent to assume responsibility for real social life, and then learn about rights and duties, and the behavior of students in the secondary stage is characterized by a rush of thinking And quick decision-making without showing deliberation and slowness and being aware of all aspects of the problem, as a study indicated. The control of impulsions towards small rewards or simple temptations will in turn acts upon instant gratification delay and the endeavor to bring about long-term objectives, which shows the ability of the student to curb his aspirations for worthless when compared with subjects of high value that may achieve social, academic or psychological goals, and perhaps materialistic professionalism, so the student begins to follow a state of self-regulation by shaping the way he deals with the specific goals in front of him, while the weakness of inhibition of the response underlies a number of cognitive problems and difficulties, so that a number of individuals respond in an impulsive manner to stimuli that are not of any importance. The BJorklund, D.F & Harnishfeger (1993) scale was adopted to measure the inhibition of the impulsive response, and the aim of the research is to identify the inhibition of the impulsive response, as well as to identify the differences in the gender variable. A sample of (300) male and female secondary school students was chosen. The findings shows that the secondary school students (fourth and fifth intermediate classes have the ability to inhibit the response), and there were differences according to the gender variable in the fourth and fifth classes).

1. Introduction

The secondary stage is an important and decisive stage in a person's life, especially if we know that it is complementary to the stage of adolescence and the various physiological and biological changes that follow that afflict a person's psychological and social life, and this is like preparing the adolescent to assume responsibility for real social life, and then learn about the rights and duties, and notice the behavior of students in the secondary school, the impulse in thinking, the speed of taking the decision, slow down and be aware of all aspects of the problem, As the study (McCauley, 2008) indicated that response inhibition is related to a number of mental decisions, especially working memory, through which the important information is processed. Secondary stimuli, especially cognitive regulations, form one of the cognitive functions, as they work to organize information and stimuli and facilitate the process of dealing with them. (Mcauley, 2008: 521)

The cessation is the basis for executive functions, as well as the working organ and task transfer, as it helps with working memory to retain, process and retrieve information, and isolating, organizing and removing unimportant stimuli and focusing on stimuli of the highest importance makes the individual pay attention to these stimuli and neglect others in order to understand and assimilate them (Wiecki, 2013: 335). As the student is able to change new ideas and concepts instead of the previous information in the memory through cognitive palm, that disruption of the palm can lead to several disturbances in the mental behavioral and emotional side, for in the emotional side it can lead to depression Mood disorder, in turn, leads to disturbance of organization and information processing. Cognitive inhibition can be described as the ability to curb and treat experiences and information not related to the situation that requires attention and then neglects it, and the appropriate response to the situation is chosen and the inappropriate responses are removed and suppressed, and this enables separation from treatment of lots of everyday Information (Reck, 2000: 68).

The weakness of response inhibition leads to cognitive interference and difficulty in dealing with external stimuli that the individual is daily exposed to, which causes him to face problems in organizing the stimuli and determining the most important of the stimuli. While holding back the less important tasks and focusing on the important ones. Harnishfeger & Bjorklund, 1993: 28)). Inhibition also stops and delays automatic responses to avoid interference between stimuli, allowing for the handling of priority tasks (Wiecki, 2013: 335). The

inhibition of response is evidence of the development of executive functions, as Diamond (2002) and others point out that inhibition is a fundamental factor in academic success and failure (Diamond, et al, 2002:355).

Impulsive response and the inability to inhibit reckless responses leads to difficulties in attention and focus on the basic factors of the situation and faces difficulties in processing and gaining experience and information (Carlson, & Moses, 2001: 1032). Students who have a weakness in inhibiting response face future academic and behavioral problems, such as aggression, academic failure, and poor attention, information processing and retention (Brittany, et al, 2009: 315).

Neuroimaging studies have indicated that areas of the prefrontal cortex brain have control over the inhibition of response, which develops through life stages (Kochanska, et al, 1996: 493). (Zelazo, et al, 2004) indicate that individuals who suffer from poor self-discipline, especially in impulsive behavior, face a problem in directing their behavior towards specific goals, and this negatively affects not only the academic reality, but also their personal and social adaptation, as fixing the response is one of the functions. Executive functions are strongly linked to academic readiness, which indicates that inhibition of response has a fundamental role in developing abilities, especially in childhood, to regulate children's behaviors and emotions. (Zelazo, et al, 2004: 170).

The study (August and others, 2000) indicates that response inhibition is negatively related to impulsive behavior, while positively related to social behavior (Hughes, et al, 2000: 43). There is no doubt that the weakness of inhibition of the impulsive response underlies a number of cognitive problems and difficulties, as many individuals respond in an impulsive manner to stimuli that are not of equal importance. Chaubertain, et al., (2005: 410) show that inhibition of the impulsive response has an important role in the domain of attention, memory and intelligence, as well as its role in social competence and emotional regulation. Diamond & Taylor (1996: 317) indicate that the weak inhibition of response is evidence of poor control of impulsive behavior. Impulsive behavior: Individuals who displayed aggressive behavior were more vulnerable to controlling and inhibiting response (Raijmakers; et al, 2009: 1009).

As indicated already, the individual works to direct behavior by controlling impulsivity and recklessness in thoughts and activities, as we find that there are many ideas that are suppressed to be replaced by many ideas and behaviors characterized by deliberate selection of the appropriate behavior, which leads to controlling our emotions and in cases of anger and frustration, and that the executive functions, especially restraint, work on the suppression of habitual dominant responses, and particularly impulsivity, where impulsivity is bypassed through executive inhibition (Cherkes, et al 2005: 2).

Carlson (2001) indicates that inhibition works to suppress the reckless or unwanted impulsive response, as it works to stop the activity and inhibit it to the lowest degree, a certain behavior that he is familiar with (Carlson, 2001: 103). Planning, organizing and willpower lead to controlling impulsivity in orienting towards small rewards or temptations, and this in turn delays immediate gratification and pursuit of long-term goals, and this demonstrates the ability of the student to curb his orientations towards topics that are not of value compared to subjects of high value that may achieve social, academic, or psychological goals, and perhaps financial professionalism, and the student begins to follow a state of self-regulation by shaping his approach to the specific goals that lie before him.

Research aims

The current research aims to know: -

First - Inhibition of the impulsive response of secondary school students.

Second- Inhibiting the impulsive response among fourth-grade secondary school students.

Third - Inhibition of the impulsive response among fifth year secondary school students.

Fourth - Inhibition of the impulsive response among fourth-grade secondary school students, according to the gender variable.

Fifth - Inhibition of the impulse response among fifth-grade secondary school students, according to the gender variable.

Methodology and procedures

The current research is based on the descriptive method and is accurate in terms of construction and methodology and includes describing the current phenomenon and collecting and classifying data for the purpose of analyzing and interpreting them in a systematic, objective and honest way in order to achieve the research objectives.

The research community

The current research community is limited to secondary school students in Baghdad - Al-Karkh district for the academic year 2019-2020

The research sample

A stratified random sample of (300) students from grades four and five in the city of Baghdad was chosen by (150) students and (150) students from high school students. They are male and female students from five schools.

The research tools

The researcher relied on the (BJorklund, D.F & Harnishfeger,1993) scale to measure the suppression of the response, after the scale was adapted according to the research objectives.

The Scale

Procedures

1- Impulse response inhibition scale

Description of the scale

To achieve the objectives of the research, it was necessary to have a tool through which to identify the inhibition of the impulse response, and the scale (BJorklund, D.F &Harnischfeger, 1993) was adopted to measure the inhibition of the impulsive response, and the scale consisted of (30) items, and included three components, so the first component (control With cognitive activity), as for the second component (resistance to cognitive interference), the third component (cognitive flexibility), and the scale includes four alternatives to the answer, which are (never - rarely - sometimes - often) and it is given to them upon correction (1-2-3-4). The maximum score that a student can obtain in the whole test is (120) points, while the lowest score is (30) and the theoretical average for the scale is (75) points.

Reliability of the scale

After completing the exploratory study, the researcher presented the positions to a number of experts and specialists in the field of education and psychology, to ensure their suitability to measure what was put in order to measure it. The validity of the positions, in terms of being correct and measuring what they were set for, and all the paragraphs got a higher rate of (80%) with some adjustments required by some experts, and thus the scale became ready for implementation.

Stability of the scale

After conducting the validation process, the researcher performed the confirmation process by re-testing, by taking a sample of (100) male and female students, by (50) male and (50) female students, then the researcher applied the test to the sample, and after a period of two weeks, the test was re-applied to the sample Itself.By using the (Pearson) equation, the coefficient of stability between the first and second application was (0, 80), and it is a good stability coefficient.

The power of distinguishing paragraphs

In order to verify the differential strength of the paragraphs, the scale was applied to the sample of statistical analysis of (200) students, then the total result of each questionnaire was calculated and classified from the highest degree to the lowest degree, then named after (27%) of the scores of the upper group and its size (54) Student and (27%) for the lower group. The researcher used the t-test of two independent samples to identify the discriminatory strength of the paragraphs and several distinct paragraphs if the calculated value (t) was greater than the tabular value (t).The statistical analysis shows that the highest calculated value (t) is (436,5), while the lowest value (t) is (2,213). This shows that all the calculated (t) values are statistically significant when compared to the tabulated value (t) of (1, 96) which means that all paragraphs are distinct between the two extreme groups by degrees.

The score of the paragraph and its relationship to the total score of the scale

The statistical analysis shows that the value of the correlation coefficient ranged between the highest value of the coefficient (0,556) and the lowest value of the coefficient (0,342). All were statistically significant when compared to the critical value of the correlation coefficient (0,139).

The degree of the paragraph and its relationship to the overall degree of the field to which it belongs

To verify this, the researcher used the correlation coefficient (Pearson) to calculate the relationship between the score of the paragraph and the overall score of the dimension to which it belongs. The value of the high correlation coefficient was (0.456) while the lowest correlation coefficient was (0.234), which had a statistical significance when compared to the value of the correlation coefficient table.

Statistical tools

In the current research, the researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences program to analyze data, including a t-test for one sample and a t-test for two independent samples and a Pearson correlation coefficient.

Results

First: - To identify the inhibition of the impulsive response among secondary school students: -

The average degree of inhibition of the impulse response among secondary school students was (93,452) degrees and a standard deviation (11,347), which is greater than the theoretical average of (75) to know the significance of the difference between these two averages and using the T-Test for one sample, it became clear that the difference was statistically significant at the level (0.005) if the calculated T value (27,480) was greater than the tabular T value (1.96), Table (1) Explaining that, this result indicates that there is no statistically significant difference at the level of (0.05) between the average inhibition of the impulsive response of secondary school students and the theoretical average for this behavior.

Table (1)
Inhibitory of the impulsive response of high school students

Sample	Sample Size	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Theoretical Mean	T Value		Indication Level
					Calculated	Tabular	
Males Females	300	93,452	11,347	75	27,480	1,96	0.005

Second: To identify the inhibition of the impulsive response among fourth-grade middle school students:

The average degrees of inhibition of the impulse response among secondary school students reached (90,673) degrees and a standard deviation (10,732), which is greater than the theoretical average of (75). To know the significance of the difference between these two averages and by using the T-test for one sample, it became clear that the difference was statistically significant at the level (0.005) if the calculated T value (25.319) was greater than the tabular T value (1.96), Table (2) Explaining that, this result indicates that there is a statistically significant difference at the level of (0.05) between the average inhibition of the impulsive response of secondary school students and the theoretical average for this behavior.

Table (2)
Inhibitory of the impulse response among fourth-grade high school students

Sample	Sample Size	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Theoretical Mean	T Value		Indication Level
					Calculated	Tabular	
Males Females	300	90,673	10,732	75	25,319	1,96	0.005

Third: To identify the inhibition of the impulse response among fifth-grade secondary school students:

The average degrees of inhibition of the impulse response among secondary school students reached (95,892) degrees and a standard deviation (10,943), which is greater than the theoretical average of (75). To know the significance of the difference between these two averages and using the T-Test for one sample, it became clear that the difference was statistically significant at the level (0.005) if the calculated T value (33,109) was greater than the tabular T value (1.96), (see Table (3) Explaining that). This result indicates that there is no statistically significant difference at the level of (0.05) between the average inhibition of the impulsive response among fifth-grade students and the theoretical average for this behavior.

Table (3)
Identifying the inhibition of the impulsive response among fifth-grade high school students

Sample	Sample Size	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Theoretical Mean	T Value		Indication Level
					Calculated	Tabular	
Males Females	300	95,892	10,943	75	33,109	1,96	0.005

Fourth: - To identify the inhibition of the impulse response among fourth-grade high school students according to the gender variable:

It is clear by using the T-Test for two independent samples that the difference was not statistically significant at the level of (0.05), as the average scores of male students on the scale of inhibition of the impulse response was (86,456) and with a standard deviation (11,921), while the average scores of females on the scale of inhibition Impulsive response (95,438) and a standard deviation (12,532), and the calculated T value (162,3) was lower than the tabular value (1.96), and Table (4) illustrates that. This result leads to the fact that there is a statistically significant difference between the average scores for males and females and in favor of females.

Table (4)

The mean, standard deviation, and the calculated and tabular T-value to inhibit the impulsive response among students of the fourth grade of high school according to the gender variable:

M	Sample Type	Sample Size	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	T Class	
						Calculate d	Tabular
1	Males	150	86,456	11,921	298	3, 162	1,69
2	Females	150	95,438	12,532			

Fifthly: - To identify the inhibition of the impulsive response among fifth-grade high school students according to the gender variable:

Using the T-Test for two independent samples, it is evident that the difference was statistically significant at the level of (0.05), as the average scores of male students on the scale of inhibition of the impulse response was (85,348) and with a standard deviation (11,932), and the average scores of females on the scale of inhibition of response impulse (91,838) and a standard deviation (10,732), and the calculated T value (4,452) was greater than the tabular value (1.96), and Table (5) illustrates that. This result leads to the fact that there is a statistically significant difference between the average scores of males and females, and in favor of females, they are less impulsive than males.

Table (5)

The mean, standard deviation, and the calculated and tabular T-value to inhibit the impulsive response among the fifth stage of high school students according to the gender variable:

M	Sample Type	Sample Size	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	T Class	
						Calculated	Tabular
1	Males	150	85,348	11,932	298	4,472	1,69
2	Females	150	91,838	10,732			

Conclusion

Discussion of the Results

Through the foregoing in the first objective that the research sample in the current study has the ability to inhibit the response, and the results of the current study are consistent with the results of the study (Carlson, S & Moses, L (2001), the study showed that there is a positive correlation between response inhibition and a number of psychological variables. A number of studies have indicated that respondents have a positive association with working memory, and this enables them to isolate stimuli that are not of equal long-term importance, and they also have an interest in ensuring excellence and achieving high academic achievement.

As indicated by the Diamond A & Taylor.C study (1996) that there is a positive correlation between the ability to inhibit the response and the academic achievement of students, as students who wish to discourage response focus on academic tasks and avoid any factors that distract attention, which prevents them from completing the tasks, as they tend to make greater efforts to perform their duties and waiving interim goals to achieve academic goals, and to obtain high marks.

A number of studies have indicated that there is a positive correlation between a number of inhibition of response and achievement motivation among students, and despite the variation in the results of previous studies according to the variation of its objectives, it confirms the existence of a link between response inhibition and a number of variables, some of which are task shifting and achievement motivation.

It is evident through the fourth goal of inhibiting the response according to the variable of sex, that there is a statistically significant difference between males and females for fourth and fifth grade students, in contrast to the study (Cherkes - Julkowsk) to the existence of a statistically significant difference in the ability to (Cherkes - Julkowsk) between males and females in favor of Females. While the study of Pampotti and Krapink, Harnischfeger, K, K, & Pope, R, S, (1993) indicated the absence of a statistically significant difference between males and females in delaying general gratification.

It is evident from the above representations that male and female students are characterized by the ability to inhibit response(Harnishfeger, K, K, & Pope, R, S, 1993). As for the second goal of discouragement among fourth grade students, it was found that students are characterized by inhibition of response.As for the third goal of discouragement among fifth-grade students, the students were characterized by the ability to inhibit response. In the fourth goal and the fifth goal of inhibiting response according to the gender variable, it became clear that there is a difference according to the gender variable and in favor of females.

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Author Information

Dr. Jafar J. Jwad
